

ISSN: 2456-5474

RNI No. UPBIL/2016/68367

VOL.- X , ISSUE- IV May - 2025
Innovation The Research Concept

Numismatics: An Effective Tool to Reconstruct the Past

Paper Id : 20263 Submission Date : 2025-05-09 Acceptance Date : 2025-05-21 Publication Date : 2025-05-25

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.16406058

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Manjeet Singh

Assistant Professor
History
S.D. College
Barnala, Punjab, India

Abstract

This research paper focuses on the incredible tool of archaeological discovery of coins. It holds that the coins as the part of material culture in historical mirror need to be analyzed in its theoretical structure with its importance and in addition, we ought to know how the study of coins is helpful in reconstructing the history and how it fills the gap of disturbed historical chronology. Moreover, the question is how the concerned study is effecting the recreation of bygone times at present. Numismatics is mainly associated with the economic aspects of contemporary times but broadly observing it, we find it significant in evaluating social, religious, political, cultural, administrative, lingual and architectural themes. Idea of currency indeed is one of the biggest innovations of human's mind. A coin, since its advent in ancient past no doubt has been transforming human life given trade, commerce and other forms of transactions desired by state in particular and man in general. The study of coins is the most relevant in those countries where we do not get a good layers or a resound chronological system to trace our historical roots. So, this research paper mainly focuses on the Indian numismatics and attempts to know how the study of numismatic has come to aid to fill the gaps of Indian historical framework. Today this study holds huge relevance given background of Indian historical traditions

Keywords Numismatics, coins, feudal order, mode of exchange, hoards, deities, and punch marked coins, etc

Introduction

The word Numismatics acquires the origin from Latin word *numisma/numismeta*[1], which means currency. In Indian context it is called *mudra-vidya*, and in dictionary meaning is the study of coins[2]. This term is associated with the metal currency of economic relevance.

The study of coins played a significant role to analyze the material past with human interface. It has a long history as numismatics came into existence after three long ages namely Stone Age, Bronze Age and Iron Age. With the evolution of this system, man managed the great empires and with this framework, big trading or commercial activities were facilitated. In this formative period of numismatic which deals with the study of coins, consequently formed the part of the development of new thoughts and techniques.

Today, the studies of numismatic are influenced by socio-political and cultural values and good source for writing of a particular time. The study of coins largely reflected upon the economic and artistic aspect of history. It marks the essential growing human beings in terms of economy and art prevailing in contemporary times.

The numismatics plays very vital and significant role in re-construction of economic history of a nation or state. It also highlights various information regarding the state administration, the religion or religious centers, social perspective political setups and other such presumable contents. Numismatics is being overlooked by the historians and scholars of history. But historians must keep in mind that numismatic evidence, however, is factual. The coins can yield hard facts in a logical, mathematical, and physical sense.

Evidently, Numismatics addresses the biggest questions about the past that cannot be answered in other ways, because the written records most of the times tend to contain artistic flavors through and through. But coins always carry the authentic information with them.

Numismatics without discrimination covers all aspects of the past ranging from social outlook of the people, their customs, customaries, ethos, ethics and religious beliefs to their reliance on material means for sustenance. Many of these questions are relevant to the present time; why did any dynasty decline? How the people were affected by religious beliefs and practices?

In this context, it would be appropriate to cite an example of image of Buddha being noticed for the first time on the coins of Kusana king Kanishka[3]. G.C. Chauhan is of the opinion that a closed or a feudalistic economy is not a good scope for further investigation but a free economy provides and takes a new issues and challenges which economic thinkers have to come into a round circle[4]. Most of thinkers are negating the coins as a source of information owing to their divergent opinions regarding the coins. Some even accuse coins to have mere reflections of elite gentry which is why they consider coins less relevant for learning the history of common masses. Clearly, such an assertion has bleak scopes. Coins, even if they symbolize the royal authority alone, have much to tell of social and other conditions prevailing at those times.

There was no compulsion of the time binding on the rulers of Kusana and Indo Greeks to engrave the coins with the image of the ruler, deities and the like albeit they had set up the rule over the north western part of India. It was the need of the time to put their local languages and religious icons to be put down on the coins for better management of the trade and commerce as these coins solved most of regional problems of these territories at that time. Coins facilitated trade and commerce and in order to differentiate the coins of one particular place from the other, it was necessitated that some insignia to provide it a distinct identity be inscribed to it.

Objective of study

There are multiple objectives for the study of this field, because this field of study highlights various stages of the past such as origin and development of the Indian Numismatics, origin of coinage and its uses, political significance, economic significance, religious affiliations, linguistics developments and administration etc.

Review of Literature

The economic thought of any civilization was the reflection of the life of human of that age. In India, transactions started through the barter system and subsequently it was replaced by a full-fledged system of currency revolutionized by the evolutionary stages of the coins. Metals were crucial for making of the coins and necessarily had the equivalent currency value. Punch marked coins being traced to 6th Century B.C.E. mainly has great historic importance. This phase not only was distinct because of coins being used for economic transactions but had its relevance in material progress in social periphery. Archaeologists and numismatists found a number of large hoards of coins. After that, a long journey started to look into the Indian past. Through these coins, the great success of man during that time was reflected. He solved the basic problems of buying the goods and items and trade and commerce got a boost beyond a considerable level. For example the great Kusana and Gupta age reflected the big hub of the trade and commerce by issuing a large number of coins for trade and big transactions. These studies also provide the reflections of the downfall of money through the study of its weights and measurements and its qualitative and quantitative processes. Numismatics painted clear pictures of alloys being used to mint coins by mixing metals in fixed proportions.

The Indian currency after punch-marked coins might have been influenced by Greeks. The Greeks were followed in North West part of India by the Scythians, Parthians and Kusanas in succession. Punch marked coins bear numerous symbols, for example bird, animal, human figure, tree, hill, river, sun, crescent, wheel, etc. the exact significance of many of the symbols remains vague. These coins informed us about the flora and fauna of its age.

Main Text

In Indian perspective, the Harappan civilization is attributed with the mode of exchange of agricultural products because a lot of evidences are found in the Harappan sites of granaries and storehouses. On the other hand, their seals were the authenticity of their authority. In the Vedic times, the people were leading the pastoral life. At that time the cow was the medium of exchange for their

transactions. In addition in the *Aitareya* Brahmana, wealth is frequently estimated in terms of cows. Afterword, the cow was the medium of transactions till the later Vedic times until the uses of metal currency was initiated. Advent of metals led to the idea of coins being used for currency. Coins were the most portable media of exchange. However, the question was whether which metal should be used for a good currency and what weight system should be used. In a general theory, there were three weight and sizes were running/used in India: the first one was Indian standard weight and the second one was Greek and last one was Persian now modern name is Iranian weight standard. Indian weight standard known as ratis, Greek- drachm and Persian was siglos. In India the regional seed was served as a medium of weight standard in these respective countries to evaluate the making of coins, besides a variety of seeds were used in the different regions in these empires or dynasties according to their easy availability. Then, a value was decided for every coin like gold, silver, copper and glass. It was the good phase to improve the trade and commercial activities to flourish their wealth and earn money more and more. After that a stamped coins started to be used in their original shapes anywhere for trading.

In the case of Indian history, scholars are still facing so many difficulties to look into its past. But the study of numismatics enables a crystal clear vision to scholars. Indian history lacks for chronological layers of its past. It does not mean that Indian did not write their history. They wrote a classical literature of their living style; most of Indian literature deals with the religious way of life not political events. That is why most of foreigners state that Indians did not know the writing of history. In my opinion the living style of western countries were different from south Asian countries. So western scholar interpreted ancient Indian historical writing in the way they wanted to interpret it to suit them. Our social or cultural life was completely different from the western countries.

Political and Administrative Significance:

In India we do not have much literature about ancient past which can provide us with authentic historical evidence for present utility. We fall short of information about the kings or rulers, their dynasties, names, their facts and works. Interestingly, we find this information with the help of the study of the coins. It can be thence surmised that Numismatics bridges the gap in reconstructing our past. Therefore, coins have a great significance for the study of the history of our ancient past. After the decline of the Mauryan empire foreigner's invasion started then they developed the mints in Indian Territory and Indian coinage started on the eyes of the foreigners rule. For example, in the case study of the Indo-Greek rulers in India, we do not have any particular idea from literature that how many of these rulers ruled in India. Through the information form coins, there were mainly 38 kings who ruled over the Punjab region about 200 B.C.E. to 100 B.C.E. We do not have much information about these from classical writers. This remarkable period is relevant equally to India and Greek. Nearly the 200 years can be envisioned only with the help of the coins in the shape of gold, silver and copper. The coinage of Indo-Greek rulers was at later times emulated by the Scythian and Parthian invaders, those who pursued their footsteps. On the other hand, the study of the coins gives the principal information about the different tribal, city republics, and monarchical states that ruled in Indian regions before and after the Common Era.

Even in the history of any particular dynasty known from other sources, coins are similarly important; the literary or epigraphical information of south Indian dynasty of the Satavahanas are confirmed and supplemented only by their coinage. Through these coins we can identify their ruling areas where they ruled. If we talk about the Kusana dynasty, it was spread in the regions, Mathura and its adjoining areas to the inner parts of the central Asia, and it has only been asserted on the basis of hoards of coins found in given areas. The extent of these hoards marked the boundaries of the empires. Even the Great Indian king Asoka from Mauryan dynasty, his empire had been framed through his important and valuable inscriptions, where Asokan inscriptions were found, we hoped that such areas were under direct control of the Asokan Empire. As a matter of fact, coins come to aid in recognizing the regions of king's empire. The Gupta dynasty's coins were found in the region of Gangetic plains, from Punjab to Bengal and adjoining areas of Orissa, Gujarat or Madhya Pradesh. In Gujarat region we found silver coins on the image of lion types. It does not mean that where the coins

were found that areas were under the influence of that king or queen, but it is quite apparent that these coins were carried through the trading activities. Like Roman coins were found in the coastal area of south India, it indicates that Roman trading activities were carried with those regions. Harappan seals were found in the Sumerian civilization (present Iraq) it means that they were engaged with commercial activities. If we talk about the Youdhays' coins, we found their migration from Dehradun, Saharanpur to Rohtak region. In first century AD they settled in Dehradun and after that they migrated from that area to Rohtak because we found their coins into the layers through excavations from those regions. In addition, we can say confidently that in the third and fourth century AD Rohtak was the main capital of their dominance; a huge city was founded.

In early stage this currency issuing authority was associated with merchant-guilds and corporate bodies and not with the royal service. Afterwards, minting system was the hegemony of the state control.

Religious Reflection

In the matter of religious history, coins played an interesting role to highlight their religious cults and beliefs. The coins of Kusana dynasty which ruled in India and the parts of north-western regions along with the adjoining areas of central Asia in the 100-200 common era. These coins bear the effigies of a number of Greek, Iranian, Buddhist and Brahmanical gods and goddesses. They not only were the popular deities worshipped amongst the people where they ruled, besides it gives the light on the development of various pantheons and their iconographic variety. It is the authentic fact the popularity of Buddha is also reflected on the coins. The symbols of Buddha in human form are seen for the first time in the study of Kusana coinage. Side by side initial representation of Hindu God Shiva and Buddha in human form with his four hands is also available on the coins of Kusana. Afterwards, they have included *Saivite* pantheons like Uma, Visakha, skanda and mahasena. The famous god of Hindu religion, Vishnu in the four handed form is noticed on the coins of Kusana king Vasudeva.

On the coinage of the Gupta dynasty, we found a rich religious framework of their time. The various forms of Hindu goddesses, Lakshmi, Durga and Ganga were highlighted in coins. The various forms of the Lama on these coins characterize the development of the iconographic form of that deity. On the other hand the numismatic representation of the deities, which was after presumably based upon early inscriptions give us an idea about the ancient stages in the evolution of image making.

Coins are the reflective index of the society. They provide vision of ethnic approaches of the different times, and manifest their social conduct. Also Coins give the indication of cultural transitions from particular dynasty to the next. It is the good example of early Gupta coins, these coin are the reflection of borrowing the dressing sense of the Kusana dynasty. After sometimes, Gupta issued Indian type of wearing dresses coins. Also coins reflect upon the various themes of societal affairs. A coin showing a Gupta ruler with a musical instrument, *Veena* on the averse of a coin and goddess Lakshmi on the obverse of the coins, depict the outlooks of the rulers with respect to the society.

Lingual Historic Significance:

Early Indian coins(punch-marked) are the land mark of the symbols only but by the time we find a good script, it is identified by regional variations, in the north west of Indian regions Greek, Kharosthi and a little bit Brahmi script has been found on the other Kharosthi script has been inscribed on the coins. It means that this part of the world was well aware of those scripts. In extreme south a lot of roman coins were found, these coins indicate that roman and south Indians were engaged in the trade relations. It is well known that Kharosthi was widespread in North West parts although Brahmi was popular in the rest of the country. These coins were landmark of the bilingual scripts. An interesting thing is that the decipherment of Brahmi and Kharosthi scripts has been done (1836-1837) through the study of numismatics by James Prinsep when he became the secretary of Asiatic Society of Bengal. After that job, James Prinsep recognized King Asoka as Piyadasi and through this act a good land mark had approved in

the chronology in the Indian history with the help of Asokan R.E. XIII. There are a number of coins, which are the reflection of the literary evidences of that time. It is the great source to find out the history of any era.

Conclusion

It is quite surprising that the study of Numismatics has been isolated and segregated and coins are not being used as a source of historical evidence to the extent it should have been. Coins have confined to the article of antiquity and embrace the walls and galleries of art museums of anonymous organizations and educational institutions. Approach towards Numismatics has been discriminated resultantly; this study fails to aid the work of research and reconstruction of history. No particular streams have been attributed to the sole study of Numismatics. No faculties have been introduced in Universities to teach or research into Numismatics.

Coins are the flashing inquiry into image, text and material gain, each of them can be considered independently. These are the multi-disciplinary sources. Coins are the pure historical and as well as archeological evidence. It is the mark of authenticity of issuing society at that time as a real document.

As a result, coins mainly represent the artistic and stylistic value and the picture of the historical proceedings. Today, coins are found on the mainly historical sites and open fields. These are the part of our cultural material and these must be studied like other material sources of archaeological importance. However, if the question rises on the base of archaeological evidence it can give more than answer to other objects of the cultural material of our past.

It would be no exaggeration if we say that Numismatics alone can catalyze the process of recreating and restructuring past proviso it gets an indiscriminate attention.

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